

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ON THE INFLUENCE OF CLASSICAL PERSIAN POETRY ON LATER WESTERN WRITERS: FROM ATTAR, RŪDAKĪ, HĀFĪZ, AND RŪMĪ TO MILTON, GOETHE, AND PLATH

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Abstract

Characteristics of Persian poetry are evident throughout Western literature. This study examines the extent and manner of the concepts, significant pieces, history, and literary influence of ancient Persian poetry that inspired the work of later Western authors. We identify those earlier works and those who created them. We discovered elegant and thoughtful expressions of themes older than civilization itself. Our premise is that readers may understand better how Persian literary traditions affected and continue to affect Western literary works and how an investigation of the concepts, stories, and poetic forms that travel from East to West may add depth and breadth to our appreciation of global literature and the generally unfamiliar cultures that created them.

Keywords: Attar, Ferdowsi, Hāfīz, Omar Khayyām, Persian poetry, *Rubāiyāt*, Rūdakī, Rūmī

Introduction

European and American secondary school and first-year university history classes will typically study the foundations of Western civilization from a Greek perspective. Philosophy implies Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle. Literature suggests Sophocles, Euripides, and Aristophanes. Graduates may receive their diplomas never having heard of Sufī mysticism, Rūdakī, Hāfīz, Rūmī, or other traces of the Classical Persian era to which many Western writers may be indebted.

This study aims to reach back into the cultural and literary backdrop of the poetry of the Classical Persian era, exploring its significance, with a particular reference to its influence on those in the West who wrote centuries after that unique period of literary history. Why Persian poetry? What is it about Persian literature that enthalls, delights, and inspires writers even after a millennium, especially Persian poetry? (LOC, 2023). “Poetry is the most significant artistic achievement of Persia,” according to Yarshater (1962, p. 610). The impact of classical Persian poetry on Western writers has been a recurring but understudied aspect of literary history (Browne, 2019; Javadi, 1983; Yohannan, 1984).

Persian poetry has permeated Western culture as no other has ever done (Yohannan, 1952). This study investigated the profound influence of Persian poetry on Western literature. In the domain of cross-cultural literary studies, comprehending the impact of Persian

poetry on Western literary traditions is of immense importance. We aim to contribute to a broader understanding of the interconnections between literary traditions by exploring this theme.

The scope of this research primarily focuses on delving into the thematic resonance, adoption of stylistic elements, and specific examples of Persian influence within the works of Western authors. Through this meticulous examination, our objective is to unveil the multifaceted ways in which Persian poetry has shaped and deepened Western literary traditions.

First, we must admit to one significant limitation of our research. That limitation is simply that one author does not read Farsi, the language of Iran, or Arabic, the language in which much of the literature of the Persian Classical era was written. It is, therefore, a practical necessity that we rely on the best available translations. We are, however, confident that the translations we use, having been subjected to centuries of review and critical comment, are sufficiently credible to allow our study to rest on valid and reliable representations of the originals. At the same time, we can understand any negative commentary owing to that limitation.

While a detailed analysis and application of the adage that “translation is interpretation” (Reynolds, 2011) is beyond the scope of this study, the reader may pursue the matter further by comparing and contrasting translations of Persian poetry by A. J. Arberry, Peter

Avery, John Heath-Stubbs, and R. A. Nicholson (2007/1918) (Windfuhr & Workman, 1973), and others. Such studies will likely find differences in connotation, as well as variations based on the nuances inherent in the source literature, all consonant with the post-structuralist perspective, as described below in the Methods section of this paper.

The Persian literary tradition, which has had a significant impact on the evolution of Western literature in many ways, is based on the cultural legacy of Persia (modern-day Iran) (Hanaway, 1993). From story translations to the adoption of Persian literary forms and themes, this article seeks to shed light on the profound and long-lasting influences of Persian poetry on the canon of Western literature (Panah, 2023). Our working hypothesis is that a significant amount of what we call “Western Literature” is related to, or even directly derived from, Persian writers, whose works shaped the thoughts of later writers, especially those in Europe and America, and which continued to have an impact well into the twenty-first century, albeit one that was frequently quiet and unnoticed.

Methods

A founding theoretical perspective of this research is that, when we translate between languages, it is imperative to engage a text in the milieu of the writer’s life and times when translating in order to avoid the trap of word-for-word translation, which misses the subtleties and nuances peculiar to the author’s culture. We respect the opinions of those who believe a work should be read apart from the events of the day, detached from the life and times of the author, that the work should stand on its own, i.e., “the author is dead” (Barthes, 1977). We disagree. Consciousness of the writer’s environment can improve the reader’s understanding and appreciation of the work, bridging the gap between implication and inference. In this case, it involves knowledge and understanding of the often violent past of Persian social, political, and economic events and the literature born of those events in the Classical period. This research, therefore, encompasses both the texts themselves and current events related to ancient Persian life, including but not limited to its internal and foreign conflicts.

Poststructuralism is the literary theory that serves as the underpinning of this study. A poststructuralist perspective of ancient Persian literature can aid our analysis, comprehension, and evaluation of these historical writings. It offers a philosophical approach that recognizes language’s inherent volatility and the ways in which social, historical, and cultural settings alter it. Poststructuralism challenges scholars to examine more closely the conventional interpretations and meanings associated with the literature that may be obscured by cultural biases, including those arising from racial and religious prejudice. In the present study, such prejudice is manifested in the term “Orientalism” (Said, 1995). This method allows for a greater understanding of the historical context in which knowledge, power, and identity were created and disputed during the creation of ancient Persian literature. A wide range of perspectives and a thorough examination of these works are made possible by poststructuralism’s emphasis on the

changing nature of meaning and the reader’s participation in the process of interpretation (Caplan, 1989).

The scope of this research focuses primarily on delving into the thematic resonance, adoption (or adaptation) of stylistic elements, and specific examples of the influence of selected Persian poets of the Classical era as seen in the works of later Western authors, mainly British and American. Through this detailed examination, and based on the theoretical foundation of poststructuralism, our objective is to unveil the multifaceted ways Persian poetry has shaped and enriched Western, i.e., English literary traditions.

What we may not always do, and what we recognize as a limitation of the study, is a close reading and reliable inference of all of the original Persian or Arabic texts. Instead, this study relies on the fidelity of the most prominent translators and, where it is appropriate, on their creativity in rendering those texts in English verse. One cannot, with integrity, use a mechanical translation system to provide an accurate, nuanced version of the source texts. That does not, however, mean that the translations are immune from dispute, and we expect to find evidence of such disputes in the critical literature by other expert linguists.

Results

Definitions

annihilation. A core concept in Sufi mysticism in which the self is lost to the unity of all.

divan. A collection of the shorter poems of one author.

Avesta. The sacred text of Zoroastrianism written in the Avestan language of ancient Persia.

Farsi. The Persian word for the Persian language.

gathas. Hymns in the *Avesta*, believed by tradition to have been composed by Zoroaster.

ghazal. A lyric poem with a fixed number of verses and a repeated rhyme, typically on the theme of love and generally set to music.

Persian. The English translation of *Farsi* [فارسی]

qasida. Laudatory, elegiac, or satiric poems in Arabic, Persian, or other genres of literature.

rubáiyát. A Four-line stanza of verse, usually written in a strict rhyme scheme.

spirituality. The quality of being concerned with religion or the human spirit. Assumes the duality of body and soul.

Sufi. A mystic “path” of Muslim spirituality, embracing a oneness with the deity.

transcendence. Existence or experience beyond normal or physical limits.

transliteration. Changing one script to another, as from Persian or Arabic to Roman letters.

Zoroastrianism. A pre-Islamic religion of Iran and India following the teachings of Zoroaster.

This study focused on the period between the tenth and fifteenth centuries, referred to as the time of Classical poetry of Persia (Yarshater, 1962, p. 62). This period would include the times of poets such as Ferdowsi (940-1020) and his epic poem *Sháhnámeh* (Davidson, 1998); Omar Khayyám (1048-1131) and his quatrains (*Rubáiyát*); Sanai (1080-1131), a mystical poet; Attar (1145-1221), renowned for works such as *The Conference of the Birds* (Attar, 1984/1188); Rūmī (1207-

1233) (Baeten, 2020), one of the most well-known Sufi poets, and his *Mathnawi*; Hāfez (1315-1390), for his ghazals collected in the *Divan-e Hāfez*; Sa'di (1210-1291), for works such as the *Gulistan* (Sa'di, c 1258 CE) and *Bustan*; Jami (1414-1422), with his mystical and romantic poetry (IranicaOnline.org).

Acknowledging with enormous gratitude the contributions of translators schooled in Persian and Arabic studies, careful consideration of these writers and their work may contribute to a more thorough knowledge of a historically significant legacy than most scholars in the West have offered and tended to diminish or completely ignore. Scholars and even casual readers are therefore made more accessible a greater and more nuanced awareness of the complex nature of ancient Persian culture and its textual representations that reveal themselves in the work of writers separated by centuries of time and thousands of miles of space. (See also Ansarian, 2003; Hanaway, 1993; and Spofford, 1885).

Historical Context

Before we can fully appreciate the influence of ancient Persian poetry on Western poets, we must look into the historical context of this contact. During the Achaemenid era (c. 550-330 BCE), the Persian Empire was massive, extending from Greece in the west to India in the east, promoting the transfer of ideas through trade. Persian literature influenced writers in Greece and Rome (Ballentine, 2019; Dabashi, 2015; Djinis, 2022).

Persian literature and culture were disseminated to ancient Greek and Roman writers through a variety of channels, as the Persian Empire during the Achaemenid era (c. 550-330 bce) allowed for this (Ballentine, 2019). Through their conquests, Persian kings like Darius I and Cyrus the Great brought Greek and Roman territories closer to Pasargadae, the capital of the Persian Empire. The elements of Persian culture infused the nations near and far. Trade networks, the presence of Persian ambassadors in Greek and Roman towns, and diplomatic interactions all contributed to the cross-cultural exchange of information. Herodotus, widely referred to as the "Father of History," is one well-known example of a Greek writer who documented Persian history and culture in his works, spreading knowledge of and appreciation for the Empire in the West (Djinis, 2022).

Significant Works of Classical Persian Poetry

To understand and appreciate the impact of ancient works on the literature of the West, readers must confront those earlier works. We find especially important contributions to later prose and poetry in the literature of the Classical Persian Age. In the process of identifying, analyzing, and evaluating the most significant of those earlier works, readers may discover the complex connections between concepts, themes, motifs, and styles in the two traditions (Chopra, 2014).

On first encountering Classical Persian poetry, we find extraordinary beauty and, even in translation, such a wide variety of meanings that must have inspired later writers. Such discoveries offer a greater understanding of the concept of John Donne, that "No man is an island." At the same time, these discoveries lead to the

finding that more work may lead to improvements in relations among cultures.

Rūdakī's Qasida

Among the most well-known figures in classical Persian literature was the highly esteemed poet Abu 'Abd-Allāh Ja'far ibn Muḥammad al-Rūdakī, commonly called just Rūdakī. He was born in what is now Tajikistan, in the city of Panjikent in the year 858 CE. In Persian literary history, Rūdakī, a royal poet under the Samanid Empire, is frequently referred to as the "Adam of Poets." He made significant contributions to poetry throughout this period of his life. His lyrical poetry in the Persian language had a considerable impact on the growth of Persian literature. Rūdakī's poetry celebrated love, the natural world, and the human experience. Over the years, poets like Rūmī and Hāfez who followed him were influenced by him (Tabatabai, 2010).

The common form of the qasida is a series of verses dedicated to a ruler, a patron, or one's beloved. Rūdakī was well known for the complex rhyme schemes in his qasidas, with motifs of love and respect. *Qasida*, Rūdakī's masterpiece, is a remarkable demonstration of his poetic skill and consists of odes dedicated to the palace and those who support it. Many poets have been inspired by his literary contributions to Persian, which have significantly impacted on the genre's development over the ages. The fact that he established New Persian poetry bears witness to his continued stature in the literary community (Tabatabai, 2010). The last sentence is as follows:

The Moon's the Prince, Bukhárá is the sky;
O Sky, the Moon shall light thee by and by!
Bukhárá is the mead, the Cypress he;
Receive at last, O Mead, thy Cypress-tree!

As to prosody, the patterns of rhythm and sound used in poetry, Hanaway (1993, p. 897) observes that enjambment, the continuation of a sentence or phrase from one line of poetry to the following line, is rare. In the quatrain above, there is no enjambment. Some scholars believe that there was no Persian prosody before the introduction of Arabic and Islam. Elwell-Sutton (1975) disagrees and asserts that, by the time of the Islamic invasions of the seventh century C.E., the Persians, "famous now for more than a thousand years for the wealth and profundity of their poetic expression" (p. 75), had their own style, and it may be assumed that much of what might be called Arabic prosody had already been in place before Islamization. Persian poetry is "as old as the history of the people themselves" (p. 75). Elwell-Sutton (1975) disagrees with the contention that Persian poetry of the Classic period is derivative from the Arabic tradition.

Shāhnāmeḥ (The Book of Kings) (Ferdowsi, 2016):

Persian poet Ferdowsi spent 35 years writing the epic poem *Shāhnāmeḥ*, *The Book of Kings*, in the late tenth and early eleventh centuries (UNESCO, 2006, p. 3; LOC, 2023). Composed of almost 50,000 rhyming couplets, it is considered the ultimate work of Persian poetry and the finest epic poem ever composed. Iranian mythology and history are chronicled in *Shāhnāmeḥ*, a repository of Persian cultural and national identity that

spans the country's mythical origins to the Arab-Islamic conquests of the seventh century. In an effort to preserve and honor Persian heritage and identity, Ferdowsi deliberately selected the Persian language over Arabic, which was gaining popularity at the time, to compile the tales of Persian monarchs, heroes, and legends. This epic makes this pledge very evident. The final words in the poem are,

I've reached the end of this great history
And all the land will talk of me:
I shall not die, these seeds I've sown will save
My name and reputation from the grave,
And men of sense and wisdom will proclaim
When I have gone, my praises and my fame
Ferdowsi, 2016, p. xii

The poem is valuable not just in terms of literature and language but also in terms of Iran's extensive cultural heritage, disputes over sovereignty, and persistent yearning for independence. Historians, readers, and fans have been enthralled with this timeless masterpiece for decades because it highlights Ferdowsi's enduring contribution to Persian poetry and his unwavering commitment to preserving the memories of a nation's past (Davidson, 1998).

Shāhnāme has influenced writers not only in Persia but in the wider world, as well. In Classical Persian poetry, Ferdowsi illustrates the richness of Persia's mythology, history, and culture. Heroic tales from both the pre-Islamic and Islamic eras, as well as historical Persian myths, have been a constant source of inspiration. The poem's influence is exemplified by well-known Persian poets such as Rūmī and Ḥāfīz, who drew inspiration from their storytelling and lyrical forms (Meisami, 1985). The epic poem has influenced literary traditions across time and space.

Some critics have advanced the notion that *Shāhnāme*, drawn from oral traditional poetry, is by extension somehow "by nature unsophisticated and 'primitive'" (Davidson, 1998, p.63). Davidson contests that position and asserts the legitimacy of oral poetic heritage, having tested the thesis that the epic poem shows "formulaic language" of the kind one finds in Homer's *Iliad* and *Odyssey* and Virgil's *Aeneid*. Given the absence of much ancient literature and the formidable task of the translator, we agree with Davidson's paraphrase of Giorgio Pasquali's maxim, "what is *lectio difficilior* for one period in the history of a text may be *lectio faciliior* for another" (p. 64).

Goethe (2010/1819) recognized Ferdowsi's poetic achievement (Mani, 2017). *Shāhnāme* will continue to have a lasting impact on future generations of writers owing to its universal themes and masterful writing. It also acts as a memorial to the storytelling's enduring power and capacity to cross cultural boundaries.

he Omar Khayyám Rubáiyát

If one knows nothing else of Classic Persian poetry, one surely must know some lines of the *Rubáiyát* of Omar Khayyám:

A Book of Verses underneath the Bough,
A Jug of Wine, a Loaf of Bread - and Thou
Beside me singing in the Wilderness -
Oh, Wilderness were Paradise enow!
(Quatrain 12)

Note especially the example of the quatrain's rhyme scheme: aaba, which again reveals itself in another of his famous quatrains:

The Moving Finger writes; and, having writ,
Moves on: nor all thy Piety nor Wit
Shall lure it back to cancel half a Line,
Nor all thy Tears wash out a Word of it.
(Quatrain 71).

The quatrains of Omar Khayyám's *Rubáiyát* (Khayyám, 1995) address topics of life, love, a search for meaning, and the fleeting nature of human existence (Decker, 1997). Edward FitzGerald translated Omar Khayyám's *Rubáiyát* into English in the nineteenth century (FitzGerald, 1997; Jackson, 1916). It became well-known in the West and impacted writers like Matthew Arnold (AIS, 2023; Javadi, 1971), Robert Frost (Bloom, 2004; Rosenthal, 2021; Untermeyer, 1958), T. S. Eliot (Muhammed & Muhammad, 2020; Naseri & Ghasemi, 2022; Watts, 1946). It had a profound effect on subsequent Western authors. The opening quatrain of Khayyám's *Rubáiyát* is a clarion call:

Awake! For the Sun, which dispersed to take flight
The stars in the night sky in front of him,
Drives Night from Heaven with them, and hits
The Light Shaft in the Sultan's Turret.

(Ferguson, Salter, & Stallworthy, 1997, p. 527; FitzGerald translation)

Readers in the West were first introduced to Persian poetry through Omar Khayyám's writings (Dabashi, 2015). Love, mortality, and the pursuit of pleasure resonated with the mindfulness and the searching for meaning of the era, influencing authors like Walt Whitman (Lemaster & Jahan, 2009); Ralph Waldo Emerson (Bloom & Kane, 1994; Noie, 2019; Widger, 2023; Gougeon, 1989; Kane, 1989; Yohannan, 1943), along with Lord Alfred Tennyson (Paden, 1943; Yohannan, 1942); and Robert Frost and John Steinbeck (Babayev, 2009).

Philosophers and literary thinkers like Friedrich Nietzsche (Ashouri, 2010; Salami, 2008) and Albert Camus (Dabashi, 1985; Farsian & Ghaderi, 2020) have been impacted by the existential insights and philosophical depth found in Omar Khayyám's poetry. Through its role as a bridge between East and West, Omar Khayyám's *Rubáiyát* contributed philosophical insights and exquisite poetry to Western philosophy and literature.

Addressing the limitations noted above, we may inquire about the quality of the translations of Classical Persian poetry that have been published and on which this study is based (Bubb, 2023). Fortunately, there is an authoritative paper that addresses that concern. Since much of what English language speakers might read of Classical Persian poetry has been translated by Edward FitzGerald, Taher-Kermani's conclusion of FitzGerald's translation of *Rubáiyát* is most valuable: "...Edward FitzGerald succeeded in transmitting what we may properly call an authentic Persian spirit in his *Rubáiyát*" (Taher-Kermani, 2014, p. 321). On the other hand, Taher-Kermani questions "FitzGerald's attunement to idiomatic nuance in the original quatrains attributed to Omar Khayyám." Translation is, after all, interpretation. (See Biria & Abadi, 2016.) Indeed,

Graves (1969) noted that FitzGerald's "adaptation" of the *Rubáiyát* omitted an important quatrain, one in which woman is metaphorically represented by the moon, connoting the inconstancy traditionally attributed to the Greek Titaness, Goddess of the Moon, Selene (Hesiod, c. 730-700 BCE, lines 15 and 371; Theoi, 2024), or Luna to the Romans, or, more likely, Mah or Mahi to the Persians (Pontia, 2018).

The Moon by her own nature prone to change

Varies from animal form to vegetable.

Destroy her form, you have destroyed nothing;

For what she seems survives her not yet being.

(Translation by R. Graves)

The Conference of the Birds

Birds, as we discuss elsewhere, seem to attract the interest of poets in every time and place, perhaps reflecting the universality of identifying with the freedom of the birds, unconstrained by the chains of gravity. This mystical allegory, written in Persian by the twelfth-century Sufi poet Farid ud-Din Attar, also called Attar of Nishapur, tackles themes of spiritual journeying and self-discovery (Attar, 1984/1188). Attar's writings influenced Western writers and intellectuals, such as the German philosopher and writer, Goethe (2010/1819), as well as psychiatrist Carl Jung (Ghaffarnejad & Estilai, 2011). To begin with:

Greetings, Hoopoe! You'll serve as our leader:

King Solomon relied on you.

To convey covert communications between

His court includes the attractive but distant queen of Sheba.

You knew his heart, and he understood your language.

The Hoopoe is a prominent figure in the poem, serving as both the leader and "spiritual guide" (much like the Sufi master) for the pilgrim-birds (Attar, 1984). The nightingale is a metaphor for the poet in Persian literature, and it appears in Romantic poetry from the nineteenth century (Ode to a Nightingale by John Keats in 1819, for instance) (Nilchian, 2016, p. 229). Research comparing Attar's *Conference of the Birds*, written in the twelfth century, and Geoffrey Chaucer's *Parliament of Fowls*, written in the fourteenth century, is likewise not surprising (Baeten, 2020; Marshall, 2023). While Attar's birds are on a quest for the Divine, and Chaucer's fowls meet to select mates, both reflect themes of longing, one for a heavenly state and the other for a better life in the here and now.

The Conference of the Birds (*Mantiq al-Tair* in Persian; Attar, 1984/1188), has had a significant impact on Western writers and scholars. This twelfth-century masterful example of allegorical poetry depicts the spiritual journey of the soul toward union with the Divine. Yarshater asserts that the Persian poet is primarily interested in the individual's understanding of reality rather than its outward expression (p. 62). Meisami (1985) also finds that the garden can be used as a symbol of the beautiful, the worthwhile, and the good. The *Conference of the Birds*, which revolves around a group of birds looking for their king, Simorgh, is filled with symbolism and mystery, including descriptions of the birds and their common journey, which some will complete, while others will fail. A thousand birds start, but

only thirty arrive. When they arrive, they discover that the answer to their quest is in themselves. The difficult voyage, with its constant – and winnowing – challenges, is unmistakably in the Sufi tradition an allegory of a Sufi sheikh leading his followers to union and spiritual enlightenment attained only by annihilation of the self.

Motifs and Themes

Themes and motifs—repeated aspects that allude to the themes—that are relevant in Western literature were developed in ancient Persian poetry. Themes are abstractions that convey points less explicitly. These encompass, among other things, elegy and panegyric, love themes, mysticism, history and mythology, ethics, and wisdom (Panah, 2023).

The Search for Meaning

In our research, we found many references to "the search for meaning" in the works of the Persian poets of the Classical Era. The phrase, both in the Persian poetry and in the later Western corpus, is connected to "transcendence." What follows is but a small sample.

Attar's allegorical poem, *The Conference of the Birds* (Persian: *Mantiq al-Tayr*) is quite literally a journey of the search for meaning and self-discovery, one that begins with what may appear to be a lack of understanding of the purpose of the adventure and ends with annihilation. A thousand birds commence the journey to find the answer, manifested in the mythical Simorgh, a symbol of the divine, but only thirty manage to survive the dangers. It is the thirty who succeed, and the Simorgh is seen in the mirror. The journey, like others that follow, e.g., John Bunyan's *Pilgrim's Progress* (Bunyan, 2020/1678), is a representation of the spiritual path and the difficulties one faces in the search for fulfillment.

Sufi mystic Rumi searches for meaning in *Masnavi*. His line, "What you seek is seeking you," illustrates the universal search for meaning, a quest seen universally in literature. For Rumi, the success of the quest is union with the divine, elsewhere, as in Attar, described as annihilation. As is true with much, if not most, poetry, Rumi's verses are best appreciated when they are not just read but sung and heard. In the case of Rumi, the reader may not only learn Rumi's plaintive love text but also be moved by the music, as tenderly sung by Homayoun Shajarian to the accompaniment of the traditional two-stringed tanbur played by Sohrab Pournazeri (Rumi Offerings, 2019). Evidence suggests that such music had an impact on the music of Baroque and later periods in Europe as it traveled the Silk Road (During, & Mirabdolbaghi, 1991; Levin, 2024).

Hāfez expressed the quest in his allusions to beauty, spirituality, love, and the fleeting nature of life on earth before the annihilation of the self as it merges with unity (Robinson, 2012/1883; Salami, 2008). He wrote about the universal hunger for acceptance, "Ever since happiness heard your name, it has been running through the streets trying to find you." In terms of the search for knowledge, he wrote, "The bird of the morning only knoweth the worth of the book of the rose; for not every one who readeth the page understandeth the meaning" (Robinson, 2012/1883, p. 384).

In the 13th century, Sa'di wrote of his spirituality, philosophy, and mysticism in a didactic manner in both prose and poetry (Khan, 1993; Robinson, 2012/1883, pp. 246-366). In Sa'di, we see meditations on the search for meaning, for an identification and appreciation of wisdom as he is able to recognize it. In that search, he also discovers himself. He emphasizes personal discovery and introspection. In *Gulistan*, he wrote, "...a traveler without knowledge is a bird without wings..." (Sa'di, 1258, Chapter 8, Maxim 50).

Love and Wine

Persian lyrical poetry often deals with the themes of love and wine, which, respectively, represent heavenly and earthly happiness. As has the 'loaf of bread' couplet from Rubáiyát. Persian love poetry has impacted European poets like Petrarch and the troubadours (Kay, 2014).

Ancient Persian poetry, with its traditions, often addressed and wove themes of love and alcohol into its rhymes. Omar Khayyám (c. 1048-1131) and Hāfēz (c. 1315-1390) frequently examined the ecstatic and passionate parts of love, which they associated with wine (Washington, 2000). Hāfēz embraced the thrill of both divine and worldly love in his ghazals, sometimes using the metaphor of wine to convey the intensity of these emotions. In his quatrains, Omar Khayyám expressed a hedonistic perspective by contrasting love and wine drinking with the transient nature of life. Poets have stood the test of time by using wine and love as vehicles to explore the complexities of human existence and the pursuit of joy.

Mysticism

Western artists in large numbers have adapted Sufi mystic thought to their own work. Western writers may have found Sufi poetry attractive because of its universal emotional and intellectual appeal. The works of Rainer Maria Rilke (2001/1923), Ralph Waldo Emerson (Carpenter, 1939; Noie, 2019; Saurat, 1930), and Johann Wolfgang von Goethe (2010/1819), for example, connected to the themes of Sufi mysticism. Rūmī, a Persian poet and mystic, influenced Western writers, including American poet Coleman Barks, who translated several of Rūmī's works (Barks, 2004). Rūmī's delightful "Song of the Reeds" is a superb exemplar of the kind of work that influenced later Western writers (AIMS, 2001).

Heroic Epics

Shāhnāme's stories have made an enduring impression on Western literature. Chaucer, Shakespeare, and Milton may have drawn inspiration from Persian tales of valor and chivalry. The Knight's Tale in Chaucer's *Canterbury Tales* shows the kind of courtly love and chivalric ideals seen earlier in *Shāhnāme*. Themes and motifs in Shakespeare's *Othello* and *Hamlet*, like love and jealousy, betrayal, hubris, moral ambiguity, and the inevitability of death, can be seen in Persian literature, as well. Milton's accounts in *Paradise Lost* of epic battles, such as Lucifer's rebellion against God, and moral dilemmas, such as Adam's choice to either disobey God's commandment or live without Eve, mirror, to a noticeable extent, similar themes in *Shāhnāme*. Milton asks, as does Ferdowsi's *Shāhnāme*: Who is the hero?

Literary Styles and Poesy

We start with the ghazal, a literary form that originated in Arabic literature and became popular in Persian poetry (Hanaway, 1993, p. 897). It is lyrical and emotive, with rhyming couplets, or "sher." Ghazals employ themes of love, grief, and beauty. They express strong emotions. Each couplet in a ghazal is independent and readable, so one can express a range of emotions in a single poem.

Because of its extensive literary tradition in the works of renowned poets like Rūmī, Hāfēz, Mirza Ghalib, and numerous others, the ghazal is a well-known and cherished form in the world of poetry. American poet Robert Bly skillfully blended Eastern and Western poetry traditions with the ghazal's form and themes in his anthology of poems, *The Night Abraham Called to the Stars* (Bly, 2002). As seen by his collection *The Beloved Witness: Selected Ghazals and Other Poems* (Sabitha, 2002), renowned Indian American poet Agha Shahid Ali has garnered recognition for his exceptional contributions to the English ghazal. These and other poets have demonstrated the ghazal's adaptability and versatility in Western poetry, along with its ability to convey complex emotions and cross-culturally relevant universal truths.

American and British writers' use of metaphors, symbolism, and allegory in their works is closely associated with the great literary traditions of Persia. Persian poetry has greatly influenced the development of Western literary techniques, which has led to the flourishing of these creative inventions. According to Nilchian (2016), Shelley was influenced by Persian literature (p. 222). Renowned Persian poets with a flair for metaphor, like Rūmī (Barks, 2004) and Hāfēz (TAP, 2023), are commended for their ability to convey complex emotions and ideas with vivid imagery.

Later Western Writers

When our research revealed instances in which there appeared to be close connections between Classical Persian poetry and the writings of Western writers in later centuries, we were obliged to address a further, perhaps even more difficult, question: Are these similarities connected causally or coincidentally? Were the later writers conscious of the works of the Persians, and did they seek in some way to emulate them, or did they simply use their own creativity to develop themes, motifs, and characterizations that happened to be present centuries past in the Near East? In some cases, as with Emerson (Noie, 2019) and others, the answer is clear: Those later writers explicitly acknowledge the influence of the Classical Persians. In other cases, while the similarities may be striking, we are not able to say with conviction that the influence is causal. A third assessment derives from those biological and social imperatives that are both timeless and universal, as artists of all genres strive to understand more deeply the human condition and the universal search for truth and meaning and give expression to their perspective.

From before the dawn of recorded history, humankind has struggled to understand and communicate matters of mortality, suffering, desire, and the search for truth and meaning. Indeed, man's search for meaning has caused considerable angst for millennia and can

be traced in Western literature to Aristotle (Kauppinen, 2013) and in the Nazi concentration camps of World War II (Frankl, 1949). It should not surprise the researcher, then, to find some degree of commonality from age to age, from place to place. This study finds such commonality between the ages of the Classical Persian poets, including Rūdakī (c. 858-941), Ferdowsi (c. 940-1020), Omar Khayyam (1048-1131), and Attar (c. 1145-1221), and of the later Western writers, from Milton (1608-1674) in the seventeenth century to Kurt Vonnegut (1922-2007) (Vonnegut, 1963, 1969, 1999) and Sylvia Plath (1932-1963) some thousand years later, in the twentieth century.

For the sake of clarity and further research, we created two categories of relationships between Classical Persian poetry and the work of later Western Writers. (See Talattof, 2023, for other methods of categorizing.) Category A is assigned to those Western materials that can be connected directly to the Persians. To Category B, we assign those materials that may not be directly connected to the earlier Persian poets but nevertheless bear unmistakable similarities with Classical Persian poetry, e.g., as a spiritual journey and other themes, motifs, and literary devices.

In order for a Western writer to move from Category B to Category A, we would need clear and convincing evidence, preferably in the writer's own words, that a specific work or body of work is directly connected to one or more examples of Classic Persian poetry. We have included translators on the basis that each translation is, in a sense, a new work, given that different translators make different choices, and that direct word-for-word translations may fail to capture the intended connotations and nuances of the original work; this argument is even more persuasive in the case of poetry. Here is but a sample of our findings:

Category A: Western Writers Directly Connected to Classical Persian Poetry

It is, we find, a necessary but insufficient condition for a poet to use constructions that were used by Classical Persian poets in order to qualify for our Category A. The poet, and sometimes, literary critic, must explicitly acknowledge the link to Persian poetry.

William Collins (1721-1759). In his 1742 book, *Persian Eclogues*, the highly regarded Collins attempted to write in the style of Sa'di, especially *Gulistan*. While the book was not as popular as his other works, it remains one of the earliest examples of the influence of Persian poetry on the consciousness of Western writers (Ross, 1895). Collins may not have been the first English writer to engage with the themes of *Gulistan*, including, but not exclusively, morality, love, and the search for meaning in a transient existence, but the title of his collection is itself a recognition of the novelty of Classical Persian poetry. Unfortunately, his life was cut short after "high living and dissipation" (Ross, 1895, p. 40).

Sir William Jones (1746-1794). Jones wrote *On the Mystical Poetry of the Persians and Hindus* (Jones, 2014/1792), comparing the mystical traditions of Persian and Hindu poetry. Jones highlighted the contemporary relevance to later works of the tradition of using allegory in Persian literature. He promoted to Western

readers an appreciation for Persian poetic traditions, nurturing cross-cultural dialogue in the study of world literature (Cannon, 1958). Edgerton (1946) wrote of the "versatile and fascinating personality" of Jones (p. 230) and "his phenomenal gift for languages as a schoolboy at Harrow." While at Oxford, "he threw himself with special enthusiasm into the study of Arabic and Persian" (Sitter, 2008).

Johann Wolfgang von Goethe (1749-1832). Goethe was inspired by the mysticism of the ghazals of Hafez and their delightful articulation. In his collection, *West-östlicher Divan* (Goethe, 2010/1819), he demonstrates the Persian influence with its mystical references, its philosophy, and its treatment of themes like love and emotional attachment. Close readings of the poems in his collection, as well as his *Hermann und Dorothea* (based on the story of Layla and Majnun, a classic Persian story of love), reveal similarities with Sa'di's *Gulistan* (Sa'di, c. 1258 CE), adding further evidence of Goethe's respect for Persian literary traditions, which enhances his own creative work.

Thomas Moore (1779-1852). Moore was an Irish poet of the Romantic Era, the time of Wordsworth, Keats, Byron, and Shelley. Moore was best known in the West for "The Last Rose of Summer." He also authored a poem of beauty, love, and a quest for a deeper meaning of life, *Lalla Rookh*, the title of which is a Persian name often used by Persian poets. In *Lalla Rookh*, Moore blended his own Romantic style and Irish passion with themes of classic Persian poetry, viz., closely woven narratives and lyrical sentiments (Taher-Kermani, 2019).

James Justinian Morier (1782-1849). Morier created novels in the *Hajji Baba* series, starting with *The Adventures of Hajji Baba of Ispahan* (Morier, 2007/1824). Garza (2023) notes the immediate and continuing popularity of the series among the public, as it was first published in 1824 and remained popular well into the twentieth century. That first book was followed by others with the same or similar Persian characters. The success of the *Adventures* encouraged Morier to write a sequel, *Hajji Baba of Ispahan in England* (1828), and fictional accounts about other characters within a similar Persian setting, namely *Zohrab, the Hostage* in 1832 and *Ayesha, the Maid of Kars* in 1834 (Garza, 2023).

Julius von Mohl (1803-1878). A German academic, Mohl deserves at least some credit for introducing Classical Persian poetry to the West outside of England. He is particularly recognized for his translation and analysis of Ferdowsi's epic poem, *Shâhnâmeh*. Western readers and authors can still benefit from his insightful criticism and sophisticated translation. He also published the works of Sa'di, author of the *Gulistan* and *Bustan* [*Rose Garden* and *Orchard Garden*], and Hâfiz, the master of mystical lyricism (Soucek, 2003). The Western comprehension of Persian literary forms, topics, and stylistic subtleties was further enhanced by these editions, his scholarly publications, and his reports on Oriental studies. Mohl's impact extended beyond the academic domain. His translation and commentary on *Shâhnâmeh*, for example, directly influenced Matthew Arnold's notable poem *Sohrab*

and *Rustam*, demonstrating the continuing influence of Persian literature on later Western writers (Pionke, et al., 2016).

Ralph Waldo Emerson (1803-1882): Emerson's essays, such as "The Over-Soul" (1841), show the influence of Persian mystical ideas, particularly the concept of Wahdat al-Wujud (Oneness of Being) (Essays: First Series, 1841; Poems, 1847): Poems like *Brahma* and *The Sphinx* reflect the influence of Persian themes and imagery (McMichael, et al., 2004, pp. 819-930; VanSpanckeren, 1994, pp. 26-29). Emerson connects his own commitment to transcendentalism to Sufi mysticism with themes of a search for ultimate reality unencumbered by intermediaries such as priests (Christy, 1932). Emerson, influenced by Persian poetry, admired the power of expressing thoughts. In his essay, he notes, "The difference is not so much in the quality of men's thoughts as in the power of uttering them" (Emerson, 1875, p. 222). This echoes the Persian sentiment that the expression of thoughts is what holds significance. The Persian poet Hāfiz, praised by Emerson, is noted for his frankness and aversion to hypocrisy. Emerson says of Hāfiz, "Hypocrisy is the perpetual butt of his arrows" (p. 222). Hāfiz's candidness aligns with Emerson's appreciation for authentic expression (Jahanpour, 2020; Noie, 2019).

Charles Augustin Sainte-Beuve (1804-1869). A French literary critic and essayist of the 19th century, Sainte-Beuve studied and reflected on the poetry of Rūmī (e.g., *Masnavi*). Holm (2023) asserts that Rūmī ("The Roman") was the most famous Sufi poet in the world. It is, therefore, entirely appropriate that Sainte-Beuve and other Orientalist scholars engaged Rūmī's work in translation and commentary. Sainte-Beuve also translated the ghazals of Hafez. He brought Sufi mysticism and Persian poetic imagery to his own writing (Haghshenas, 2022; Marks, 1974). Sainte-Beuve wrote about the historical development of Classical Persian poetry, including *Le livre des rois: Traduit et commenté par Jules Mohl. Tome 3* [The Book of Kings: Translated by Jules Mohl. Volume 3], a review of Julius von Mohl's work on Ferdowsi's epic poem *Shāhnāme*.

Henry Wadsworth Longfellow (1807-1882). Longfellow's 1863 collection of poems, *Tales of a Wayside Inn*, includes his poem, "The Bird and the Ship." It retells what may be one of the greatest stories in Persian poetry, Attar's strikingly beautiful, longer, and more elegant Persian Sufi allegorical poem, *Mantiq al-Tayr* [The Conference of the Birds] (Longfellow, 2018/1871). In both poems, the soul in its journey through mortal life is symbolized by birds on the wing. *The Divine Tragedy* (Longfellow, 2018/1871) has elements of Sufi mystical poetry. Longfellow was influenced by Persian poet Ferdowsi, who wrote the epic poem *Shāhnāme*. He also drew inspiration from Ferdowsi's tales and incorporated elements of Persian literature in his own poetry (Bradley, et al., 1974, pp. 1469-1506; McMichael, et al., 2004, pp. 1539-1548).

Edward FitzGerald (1809-1883). No treatment of the impact of Persian poetry on later Western writers would be complete without the acknowledgment of Edward FitzGerald. His translation of the *Rubāiyāt* of Omar Khayyam (FitzGerald, 1997/1859) popularized

Persian poetry in the West and influenced numerous poets and writers. FitzGerald's body of work in respect to Persian poetry is not limited to translation. One can see in his own poetry the Persian influence in his treatment of mysticism, love, and the impermanence of life. The romantic and philosophical elements found in Hafez's "Divan-e-Hafez" and Attar's "Conference of the Birds" ring in FitzGerald's quatrains, highlighting a harmonious amalgamation of two distinct poetic traditions. Notwithstanding some recent criticism (e.g., see Taher-Kermani, 2014), FitzGerald's translation of the *Rubāiyāt* is a vivid reminder of the enduring power of Persian poetry.

Robert Browning (1812-1889). Evidence of the influence of Persian poetry may be found in Robert Browning's 1884 long poem, or what critics call a four-part collection of verses, *Ferishtah's Fancies* (Browning, 2015/1884; Kennedy, 2017). In *Ferishtah's Fancies*, Browning employs ideas of Sufi mysticism to create stories inspired by the poetic traditions of Persia. Gal Manor (2013) examines at length the clues to Persian influence on the works of Browning in the context of the Western perception of Orientalism and how he mixed Eastern and Western elements in his poetry.

Edward Backhouse Eastwick (1814-1883). Eastwick is one of the premier translators of Sa'adi's masterpiece, *The Gulistan*, or *The Rose Garden of Sa'adi*, a collection of poems and stories drawn from ancient Persian folklore. Eastwick's translation, full to overflowing of insightful Persian wisdom, made *Gulistan* accessible to Western audiences. Eastwick also translated Sa'adi's poem *Bustan* [The Orchard] (Katouzian, 2012). In *Bustan*, Sa'adi used both poetry and prose to tell moral and ethical stories, reflecting his extensive travels and thoughts.

Henry David Thoreau (1817-1862). In *Walden* (2023/1854), Thoreau emphasized simplicity and the joys of communing closely with nature, themes evident in Rūmī and the ghazals of Hafez (Bradley, et al., 1974, pp. 1213-1468; McMichael, et al., 2004, pp. 1340-1540). Scott (2007) suggests, "The Persian dimension in Thoreau is often rather overlooked and yet one that is quite substantive" (p. 21). How substantive? A rough measure of the claim is that in Scott's paper of twenty-six pages (excluding references), there are twenty-seven mentions of the words "Persia" or "Persian." Thoreau saw value in the themes expressed by the Classical Persian poets and the power of those expressions. Themes of love and the search for meaning that Scott found in Persian poetry resonated with Thoreau and can be reflected in *Walden*, *Civil Disobedience*, and other works (Scott, 2007; Thoreau, 2023/1849 and 1854).

Matthew Arnold (1822-1888). In the context of the influence of Persian poets, Arnold is perhaps best known for his poignant and ironic poem *Sohrab and Rustam*. Drawing inspiration from Ferdowsi's epic *Shāhnāme*, Arnold pits the tempestuous Tartar youth Sohrab against the leader of the Persian army, the older Rustam. Rustam kills Sohrab in the battle. As Sohrab lies dying, they discover they are father and son. Arnold echoes themes from *Shāhnāme* and its themes of tragic conflict, heroism, and the clash of empires.

Themes in Persian literature reveal themselves in Arnold's probe of human nature as he shows with tragic results the consequences of personal and societal conflicts. "The Study of Poetry" (Arnold, 1880) expresses admiration of Sa'di, who gives prominence to the values of moral behavior and humanism, values with which Arnold identified.

Charles Eliot Norton (1827-1908). Norton's translation of *The Divan of Hafez* demonstrates his appreciation for the mystical and lyrical aspects of Persian poetry. In addition to his translations, in his own writing, he identified with the Classical Persian themes of mysticism, love, and the search for meaning. Norton expressed sympathy for the connections between Oriental and Occidental literary traditions, as evidenced in such works as *Political Writings of John Milton* (Norton, 1905) and *Studies in Dante* (Norton, 1899).

Edward Henry Bickersteth (1825-1906). "A Lament for Persia" by Edward Henry Bickersteth grieves the decline of a once-great power, an empire that was, at the time, the largest the world had ever seen, with half the planet's population (Briant, 2002):

Mourn, Persia, mourn! thy charms decay;
Proud Ispahan, the seat of power,
Is shorn by time's relentless sway
Of her rich zones and golden dower,
Which shone around her stately domes,—
That ancient gem of empire, and her sovereigns' homes.

(Bickersteth, 1848/2022)

Edward Granville Browne (1862-1926). Browne brought the brilliance of Persian poetry to the English-speaking public in his translations, especially of Rūmī and Hafez. His book, *A Literary History of Persia*, consists of four parts and 521 pages. As the subtitle indicates, the period covered is "From the earliest time to Ferdowsi," that is, from 226 CE to 1000 CE. The thirteenth-century Sufi poet Jalal al-Din Rūmī appears to have had a significant impact on Browne. As with other Western writers with an affinity to spiritualism, Browne was attracted to Rūmī's mystical poetry. The *Divan-e-Hafez* also helped to form Browne's writing, reflecting his understanding of the intricacies of Persian poetry. Through Browne's translations and interpretations of Persian poetic masterpieces, such as Rūmī's "Mathnawi" and Hafez's ghazals, he not only introduced Western audiences to the beauty of Persian literature but also demonstrated the profound impact it had on his own scholarly endeavors, fostering cross-cultural understanding and appreciation.

Arthur Symons (1865-1945). Symons translated the ghazals of Hāfiz and wrote his own poetry. *The Fool of the World* (Symons, 2010/1906) demonstrated insights into and appreciation of the form and style of Classical Persian poetry (Soucek, 2003; Symons, 2010).

James Elroy Flecker (1884-1915). *Hassan: The Story of Hassan of Bagdad and How He Came to Make the Golden Journey to Samarkand* (Flecker, 2021/1922), Flecker's romantic adventure play, was heavily influenced by Persian themes, including the hero's search for meaning, the brief nature of life, fatalism, and elements of mysticism and spirituality.

Ezra Pound (1885-1972). His poems, such as "The River-Merchant's Wife: A Letter" and "Fan-Piece for Her Imperial Majesty," are inspired by Classical Persian poetry. See also Pound (1915), a collection of translations and adaptations of poems from the Chinese Tang dynasty, which were themselves influenced by Persian poetry.

Robert Graves (1895-1985). Graves, with Omar Ali-Shah, provided an alternative to FitzGerald, a new translation of Omar Khayyām's *Rubāiyāt* as well as other Persian works (Graves, 1969; Graves & Ali-Shah, 1967).

Arthur John Arberry (1909-1999). A scholar and translator of Persian poetry, Arberry's works, including translations of Rūmī, the *Rubāiyāt* of Omar Khayyām (1952), and *Fifty Poems of Hāfiz* (Arberry, 2008/1947s), remain influential works in the scholarship of Persian poetry.

Coleman Barks (born 1937). Barks's translations of Rūmī's poetry, such as *The Essential Rūmī* (1995), have brought Rūmī's work to a wide audience in the West.

Alan Williams (born 1944). His translations of Sa'di's *Gulistan* (2000) and *The Shāhnāme: The Epic of Kings* (2011) are faithful to the original and made accessible to many.

Dick Davis (born 1945). A prominent translator, his *Blossoms of the Garden: Classical Persian Poetry* (2010) and *Faraway Music: New Translations of Classical Persian Poetry* (2019) offer discerning modern interpretations.

Category B: Western Writers Indirectly Connected to Classical Persian Poetry

In the history of literary theory and criticism, one finds themes, motifs, and conventions that are universal and, therefore, impossible to attribute to one era, including the period under investigation in this study. Nevertheless, we note for further research some of these cases.

John Milton (1608-1674). While we can find no evidence of a direct connection between Milton and the Persian poets, we find similarities in the themes, motifs, and content of both (Saleem, 2015). Any consideration of similarities would, of course, start with Milton's epic poem, *Paradise Lost*. One common theme of *Paradise Lost* and Persian poetry is the contest between good and evil, between the forces that harm vs. the forces that help. Rūmī and Attar take the reader on a spiritual journey, hoping for union with the divine. Also, in much, if not most of Milton's body of work, we see clearly what we might call an obsession with freedom, exemplified most clearly in his *Areopagitica* (Milton, 2016/1644). That theme, free will in the face of fate, or the will of the divinities, is present in much of the work of the Persian poets, which is especially clear in the *Shāhnāme* (Ferdowsi, 2016).

Harriet Beecher Stowe (1811-1896). In her historic novel, *Uncle Tom's Cabin* (Stowe, 1986/1852), Harriet Beecher Stowe joins Hāfiz in giving voice to spirituality and its expression in action in the community. Although the tie to Hāfiz may be coincidental, the theme is unmistakable.

Walt Whitman (1819-1892). *Leaves of Grass* presents Whitman's perspectives on the human condition, much as we see in Rūmī and Hafez. What we call transcendentalism in Whitman, especially in *Song of Myself*, we see clearly in the spiritual journey of the avian travelers in *The Convention of the Birds* by Attar (Bradley, et al., 1974, pp. 1705-1803; McMichael, et al., 2004, pp. 1787-1926; Khaleghi, 2019; Farzan, 1976; VanSpanckeren, 1994, pp. 30-32).

Emily Dickinson (1830-1886). In Emily Dickinson's verses, we see themes, motifs, and structures that resemble the works of Rūmī (1207-1273), Hafez (1325-1390), and Sa'di (c. 1210-1291) (Browne, 2019). Her meditations are consistent with Sufi mysticism and its themes of mortality. Her exploration of themes such as death, nature, and the metaphysical remind us of the mystical and philosophical underpinnings of Classical Persian poetry. As with Dickinson, Persian poets are remembered for their insights and expression of spiritual and existential themes. We see the connection clearly in Dickinson's metaphorical and highly anthologized "Because I could not stop for Death" (Bloom, 2004, p. 584; McMichael, et al., 2004, pp. 1926-1955); VanSpanckeren, 1994, pp. 34-35).

William Butler Yeats (1865-1939). While there may not be explicit evidence linking the work of Yeats to the Persian poets, his poems definitely take the kind of transcendental and mystical approach of the Sufi poets (Christy, 1932; Muhammed, 2020, p. 111).

Rainer Maria Rilke (1875-1926). The influence of *The Conference of the Birds* by Sufi poet Farid ud-Din Attar can be found in Rainer Maria Rilke's *Duino Elegies* (Rilke, 2001/1923). Both seek self-identity and divine wisdom as a metaphorical spiritual journey. Steps in Rilke's journey are eerily similar to the seven symbolic valleys through which Attar's birds must pass.

James Elroy Flecker (1884-1915). We see the influences of Persian poetry themes, motifs, and perspectives in Flecker's five-act play, *The Story of Hassan of Bagdad and How He Came to Make the Golden Journey to Samarkand* (2021/1922).

T. S. Eliot (1888-1965). *The Wasteland* may be seen to embrace the mystic approach to the human condition, much as the Sufi poets. (VanSpanckeren, 1994, pp. 63-65). Muhammed & Muhammed (2020) write, "Eliot's words and expressions of his early poetry do not merely sound religious but [are] quite close to the expressions of the Sufis" (p. 112). Watts (1946) makes a clear connection between Eliot and his Persian predecessors: "What is the peculiarity of the present moment? This: that, unlike past and future moments, it is not wholly contained in time. To convey this perception, Eliot uses language one must cheerfully grant that resembles the declarations of the great mystics when they treat similar topics" (Watts, 1946, p. 56).

Allen Ginsberg (1926-1997). Icon of the Beat Generation, Ginsberg shared with the poets of Classical Persia a combination of the quest for spiritual fulfillment with new styles of expression. Ginsberg was attracted to the philosophies of the East and reflected that attraction in his poems, most notably, "Howl" and "The

Fall of America," in which, like the Sufi poets, conventional norms were attacked as contradicting the laws of nature (Ginsberg, 1996; VanSpanckeren, 1994, pp. 87-88).

Sylvia Plath (1932-1963). In Plath's poem, *Lady Lazarus*, published two years after her death by suicide, we can see themes and motifs that resemble those of the modern Iranian poet, Forough Farrokhzad. Both were female, and both were influential in their time. From common experiences, then, come a style that may be seen as personal and filled with emotion, but perhaps more relevant, the themes of love, death, and rebirth (VanSpanckeren, 1994, pp. 82-84; The Gospel according to John 11:1-45). Both lived in different countries with different religions, and both attempted suicide three times. Both died at about the same age: Farrokhzad at 32, Plath at 30 (Jamali, 2008). (See also Bausani, 1960, for Europe and Iran in contemporary Persian literature.)

Discussion

This study takes up George Goodspeed's challenge when he wrote, "[T]here is much to be brought out respecting this exceedingly interesting topic" (1893, p. 153). Actually, the more we learned about the topic of classical Persian literature, the more questions we felt compelled to address and the more we were curious to find out. The literary world is still being shaped by the intricate and ongoing phenomena of ancient Persian literature's influence on subsequent Western writers. The cultural legacies of both the East and the West have been greatly influenced and informed by the flow of ideas, subjects, and literary styles between the two cultures, the two areas, and the two times. We learn more about the interdependence of world literature and the lasting influence of Persian literary traditions in Western works as we investigate this cross-cultural interchange. The influence of Persian literature on Western authors demonstrates how literature can encourage creativity across national borders as well as generational and cultural gaps.

Without acknowledging Edward FitzGerald's exposition of Omar Khayyám's *Rubáiyát*, it would be hard to discuss the influence of Classical Persian literature on subsequent Western writers (Biegstraaten, 2008; Elwell-Sutton, 1971). Readers first come across what would become the permanent legacy of the ancient Persian writers in a few passages of Khayyám's *Rubáiyát*, more so than in any other work from the same time period and location that makes up Classical Persian literature. When everything is said and done, Omar Khayyám's *Rubáiyát* has had a profound influence on Western literature, inspiring poets, philosophers, and writers to explore novel ideas and literary genres. Without a doubt, Omar Khayyám's writings introduced Western readers to the depths of Persian poetry and had a significant impact on the development of Western literature in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries.

Having noted above the limitations of translation, especially the nuances of the original, we cannot leave the *Rubáiyát* without asking how much of what comes to Western readers is the voice of Omar Khayyám and

how much is that of Edward FitzGerald. For the purpose of this analysis, we are left to recommend further research into that question.

Perhaps the simplest way to sum up Persian literature is to quote Goodspeed (1893): 'No cultivated person should be without some knowledge of it...A discussion of the influence of Persian literature on the life and thought of other nations is something that Goodspeed (p. 153) strongly advocates. Our exact thought!

This study concludes that the writers of Classic Persian literature founded a route from which later writers in prose and poetry benefitted. In light of this discovery, a university would be well advised to incorporate Persian literature into its bachelor's or master's degree programs or, at the very least, a unit within the curriculum. The institution should provide a Ph.D. program in English Language and Literature, and one or two of the best courses would be on Persian literature and its influence on Western writers.

Further research into the translation and interpretation of traditional Persian literature into the English language is not only a worthwhile scholarly endeavor in and of itself, but it may also contribute to healing the existing gulf in ties between modern Iran and the rest of the world. Persian literature has a fine history spanning centuries and is a treasure trove of information, culture, and artistic expression. While fluency in Persian and Arabic languages may be a limitation for most Anglophones, we found an abundance of Classical Persian poetry available in translation. Themes of love, unity, and the human condition are common in both Persian poetry and the writings of Western poetry. In the process of identifying and further exploring these and other themes, we are assured of finding commonalities that enlighten the reader and the writer of the current age.

By providing English-speaking audiences with greater access to this lush literary heritage, we can foster a deeper understanding of Iranian history, culture, and the universal themes that underlie these literary masterpieces. Expanded cross-cultural connections possess the capacity to cultivate compassion, bridge gaps in understanding, and facilitate more intricate and harmonic exchanges between Iran and the global community of scholars.

Because of literature's capacity to transcend boundaries and promote respect for one another and for other cultures, further study and translation in this area will be both academically beneficial and rewarding and productive as a significant step toward the development of more solid, peaceful international relations.

We should note that while the focus of this research is on classical Persian poetry, much can be learned from the study of the broader topic of the prose of the period. The 2023 piece by J. T. P. de Bruijn (2023) offers an attractive, if brief, introduction to that matter. More detailed treatments of prose work in the Classical Persian corpus may be found in Arberry (1958), Levy (1969), and Morrison (1981).

Finally, if we had encountered the marvelous work of Javadi (1983) prior to starting this study, we might have thought we were gilding the lily. However, we now believe that our work, along with that of Javadi

and other scholars, can serve to stimulate further research into the extent and manner of the connection between and among the cultural traditions that characterize the common search by pilgrims of East and West in a quest for truth and beauty in literature.

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Appendix

A Brief Chronology of Persian Poetry

c. 522 BCE
Behistun Inscription of Darius I; considered the first example of Persian literature.

522-486 BCE
Reign of Darius I The Great

490 BCE
Battle of Marathon during the first Persian invasion of Greece

480 BCE
Battle of Thermopylae between the Achaemenid Persian Empire under Xerxes I and an alliance of Greek city-states led by Sparta.

330 BCE
Literature of the Achaemenid Empire is lost in the conquest by Alexander the Great and the burning of the library of Persepolis.

224 CE-651 CE
Middle Persian dialect in use during the period of the Sassanian Empire; written literature develops in response to religious texts.

633-656 CE
The Muslim Arabs under the Rashidun Caliphate conquer the Persian Sasanian Empire, leading to the decline of Zoroastrianism and the Persian language in favor of Arabic.

651 CE
Sassanian Empire falls to invading Muslim Arabs; Zoroastrian texts and Sassanian literary works are destroyed.

750 CE-1258 CE
Persian literature and culture revive under the Abbasid Dynasty.

819 CE-999 CE
Persian literature flourishes under the Samanid Dynasty, which produces some of its greatest poets.

859 CE-c. 940 CE
Life of the Persian poet **Rūdakī**, born Abu Abd Allah Ja'far ibn Muhammad ibn Hakim ibn Abd al-Rahman ibn Adam al-Rudhaki al-Sha'ir al-Samarqandi, called 'the father of Persian Literature.'

c. 900-1600
Generally considered the Classic Era of Persian poetry

c. 935-977

Life of the Persian poet **Daqīqi**, born Abu Manšūr Muḥammad ibn Ahmad Daqīqī, who makes the first attempt at writing the *Shāhnāmeḥ*, *The Persian Book of Kings*.

c. 940-1020

Life of the Persian poet **Ferdowsi (or Ferdusi)**, born Abolghassem Mansour-ibn-Hassan Ferdowsi Tousi, author of the literary masterpiece *Shāhnāmeḥ*, *The Persian Book of Kings*.

1048-1131

Life of the Persian mathematician, scientist, scholar, and poet **Omar Khayyām**, born Ghiyāth al-Dīn Abū al-Faṭḥ 'Umar ibn Ibrāhīm Nīsābūrī.

1080-c. 1131

Life of the Sufi Persian poet **Sanai**, born Hakim Abul-Majd Majdūd ibn Ādam Sanā'ī Ghaznavi author of *The Walled Garden of Truth*.

c. 1141-1209

Life of the Persian poet **Nezāmi**, born Jamal ad-Dīn Abū Muḥammad Ilyās ibn-Yūsuf ibn-Zakkī.

c. 1145-c. 1220

Life of the Persian Sufi mystic poet **Attar** of Nishapur, born Abū Ḥāmid bin Abū Bakr Ibrāhīm.

1207-1273

Life of the Persian poet **Rūmī**, born Jalāl al-Dīn Muḥammad Rūmī.

1210-c. 1291

Life of the Persian poet and prose writer **Sa'di**, born Sa'di Shīrāzī.

1315-1390

Life of the Persian poet **Ḥāfiz** Shiraz, born Khwāje Shams-od-Dīn Moḥammad Ḥāfiz -e Shīrāzī.

1771

Sir William Jones translates poems of **Ḥāfiz**.

1853

Matthew Arnold publishes the first English translation of *Sohrab and Rustum*.

1858

Emerson publishes "Persian Poetry" in *The Atlantic*.

1859

Edward FitzGerald publishes *The Rubāiyāt of Omar Khayyām*.